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Quantitative Assessment of Landslide Risk to Residents on the Slope of a Hazardous Area in Malaysia.

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Abstract

This paper presents a Quantitative Risk Assessment (QRA) method for the impact of a landslide using a case study in Malaysia. The probability of the slope experiencing a landslide event is computed. Subsequently, the runout of the landslide in the case study is forecasted using the previously developed empirical model for Malaysia. The risk for elements at risk along the landslide's runout path is estimated. The overall risk to society is then portrayed using an F-N diagram, demonstrating the practical application of the proposed Malaysian risk criterion. In addition, the results of this analysis will serve as a foundation for conducting a cost-benefit analysis, designing risk reduction measures aligned with the established risk acceptance criteria, and informing future land use planning processes.

1. Introduction

A specific case study was selected for numerical simulations aimed at providing an understanding of the risks associated with rainfall-triggered landslides. These simulations function as an initial warning system, particularly in areas prone to severe landslides that can result in extensive devastation and potential loss of lives. To mitigate these risks to both lives and property, it becomes imperative to conduct thorough stability analyses and risk assessments of slopes within specific regions.

This paper focuses on evaluating the direct risk to life within a residential area in Malaysia. A developed empirical landslide run-out model is employed to quantify the risk of landslide run-out for elements situated downhill from the areas where landslides initiate. From the analysis, one shall see that the slope was already within the unacceptable risk region of the Malaysian risk criterion, leading to the occurrence of slope failure resulting in high casualties. In addition, the results of this analysis will serve as a foundation for conducting a cost-benefit analysis, designing risk reduction measures aligned with the established risk acceptance criteria, and informing future land use planning.

Using PLAXIS LE, the numerical model was conducted as follows: (i) Examining the transient seepage into soil slopes during an extreme rainfall scenario with a 10-year Annual Recurrence Interval (ARI); (ii) Evaluating the probabilistic slope stability associated with transient seepage induced by extreme rainfall infiltration. Through this analysis, the probability of an event of a specific magnitude was ascertained. The consequence of an event of a particular size was assessed in relation to the vulnerability of the residents by taking into account the runout distance, enabling the estimation of the annual probability of a fatality resulting from a landslide in the study area.

2. Extreme Rainfall Analysis

Rainfall records spanning the past 48 years were acquired from the Department of Irrigation and Drainage. Employing the Gumbel extrapolation technique [1], [2], the maximum rainfall anticipated within those specific days was computed for a return period of 10 years. The choice of a 10-year return period aligns with recommendations stipulated in the Geotechnical Manual for Slope in Hong Kong [3] and stands as a prevailing design standard for Malaysian slopes, as cited in studies by [2], [4].

Figure 1 displays the computed maximum potential rainfall and rainfall intensity expected over durations of 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 14, and 30 days for a 10-year return period, derived through Gumbel's extrapolation method. The data illustrates that the pattern of rainfall across various days does not follow a linear progression due to the non-uniform nature of precipitation over extended durations. The difference of rainfall intensity between day 1 and day 2 is seen to be drastic while day 2 onwards the difference is seen to be more gradual. As the total

volume of rainfall accumulates over a given timeframe, the intensity tends to diminish.

Figure 1 Intensity of Rainfall occurring at different days for return period of 10 years.

3. Numerical modelling

In this study, an unsaturated/saturated transient seepage analysis was conducted using the Groundwater component within the PLAXIS LE computer program. The simulation spanned a 30-day period, simulating of extreme rainfall condition. The analysis commences by defining the initial state as the position of the initial groundwater table, accompanied by a designated maximum negative pore water pressure head. This approach enables a more realistic execution of the analysis.

Preceding the seepage analysis, the definition of material or soil properties and the establishment of boundary conditions were necessary prerequisites. The characterization of soil properties relied on volumetric water content (VWC) functions, soil water characteristic curves (SWCC), and Hydraulic Conductivity Functions (HCF), considering both unsaturated and saturated material models. Among the numerous of available functions integrated into PLAXIS LE i.e. VWC data point function, Van Genuchten function Gardner Fit, and Fredlund-Xing function etc., this study employed the data point function for defining volumetric water content. A general SWCC specific to silty residual soil from Malaysia, as outlined in [5], was implemented in the simulation. Figure 2 (a) & illustrate the SWCC and hydraulic conductivity function utilized in the simulation, respectively. The impermeable underlying rock layer was replicated within the simulation by allocating an extremely low hydraulic conductivity value, specifically set at $1E-17$ m/s.

Figure 3 shows the slope model simulated in PLAXIS LE. The geometric configuration of the slope was subject to the following boundary conditions:

- Rainfall intensity was modeled as a flux boundary condition on the slope's surface.
- Below the groundwater table, total head boundary conditions were applied along the sides of the slope.
- Above the groundwater table, a nodal flux of $Q = 0 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ was enforced along the slope's sides, symbolizing a no-flow boundary condition.

The results derived from the seepage analysis, which portray the distribution of pore water pressure (PWP), serve as input data within the Slope Stability module of the PLAXIS LE computer program [29]. The unsaturated shear strength is computed by employing the Mohr–Coulomb failure model within the PLAXIS LE program, Details regarding soil properties can be found in Table 1.

The Alternative Point Estimated Method (APEM), is employed for probabilistic analysis [6]–[8], reduces the necessary number of analyses when employing the Monte Carlo method. APEM significantly cuts down the computational time essential for statistical analysis [7], [9]. With $2N + 1$ model runs, where N represents the quantity of model input variables, this method can compute probabilities efficiently. It particularly appeals in scenarios with numerous input variables exhibiting variance. The parameter Cohesion is assigned as a log-normal probability density function [9] while friction angle and unit weight are assigned to follow a normal distribution [1], [9]. The outcomes will be presented in terms of the probability of failure, pf. Moreover, APEM allows the depiction of results via a tornado diagram, indicating the relative impact of each input variable [8]. Consequently, it becomes feasible to ascertain both the overall probability of failure and the input variable exerting the most substantial influence on the factor of safety.

Figure 2 (a) Soil–water characteristic curve (SWCC), (b) hydraulic conductivity function

Figure 3 General profile of the slope at the case study area

Table 1 Soil properties of the slope of study

Soil Layer	Soil Type	Depth (m)	Effective Cohesion, c' (kPa)	Effective Friction Angle, ϕ (°)	Soil Unit Weight γ' (kPa)
Layer 1	Silt	0–13.5	3	26	17.5
Layer 2	Sandy gravel	13.5–17	8	32	18
Layer 3	Granite	17 onwards	10	38	18.5

3.1 Pore-water pressure results

Transient pore-water pressure variations at the middle of the slope (Section A–A') are shown in **Figure 4**. Similar PWP trend and results is seen in the documented study by [10]. It should be noted that PWP at the soil surface at the middle section became near zero after a period of 3 days of continuous rainfall for the entire period the extreme rainfall. Again, similar results were obtained by [10] where the PWP at soil surface saturates at an early phase under extreme rainfall conditions. The early saturation occurs due to the swift decline in matric suction and reduced cohesion among soil particles [10]. It's important to highlight that no positive pore-water pressure was observed at the surface during the entire simulation duration which is similar to the results in the

model by [5], [11]. The PWP (Pore water pressure) at 2 meters below the surface at section A-A' (Figure 3) never reaches zero, suggesting that the water table does not rise to that extent during the entire 30 days of continuous extreme rainfall.

Figure 4 PWP profiles for the slope at section A- A' during the simulation

3.2 Probabilistic slope stability analysis results

The changes of the Factor of Safety (FOS) with time in the simulation is shown in Figure 5. The findings from the analysis of slope stability showed a pattern akin to PWP, demonstrating a decline in Factor of Safety (FOS) from

1.18 at the initial stage, reaching near critical value of 1.04 at the end of the 30th day of extreme rainfall. Similar results were seen in documented studies related to the same slope [5], [11], [12]. As the PWP at the slope built up, the safety factor decreases. The drastic drop in FOS at the beginning can be explained by the high rainfall intensity at the beginning of the simulation as seen in Figure 1. Due to the substantial increase in water load during early stages of extreme rainfall, there is a rise in pore water pressure and a simultaneous decrease in matrix suction. Consequently, this causes a decline in the slope's safety factor. The slow and marginal decrease in FOS safety after the initial drastic drop is due to the lower value of saturated hydraulic conductivity of the soil. Overall, the observed decrease in Factor of Safety (FOS) was attributed to prolonged extreme rainfall and the subsequent redistribution of the infiltrated rainwater [5].

Figure 7 displays the most vulnerable slip surface with the minimal FOS. Following 30 days of extreme rainfall, the critical safety factor reaches 1.04 when employing the GLE solution technique. Analysis using this method indicates that the calculated safety factor just after the 30-day rainfall period hovers close to the brink of failure. In real life scenario, the same slope experienced the failure resulting in deaths due to prolonged antecedent rainfall when its FOS approach and drop slightly below the critical safety factor of 1.0 [5], [12]. This indicates that this slope will be likely to fail if subjected to 30 days continuous rainfall of 10 years-ARI. It should be noted that in real life, failure occurred at the top layer of the soil which greatly aligned with the simulation results presented in Figure 7 [5], [11].

The tornado diagram in Figure 8 shows the relative influence of the material parameters to the factor of safety value. The analysis indicates that the FOS for this slope is primarily affected by the friction angle of silt, the soil at the top layer. Following this, the cohesion of top silt layer does exert some influence on the factor of safety. However, the cohesion of the second layer, comprised of sandy gravel, alongside the materials' unit weight, has a relatively uniform and minimal impact on the slope's safety factor which is not surprising as the critical slip circle occurs only on the top soil layer of the slope. Similar results are obtained in published studies where friction angle exerts the highest influence on FOS followed by cohesion of the materials [1], [9], [13].

The probability of failure, p_f throughout the simulation is presented in Figure 6. The p_f during the initial condition is computed at 0.0786 through the APEM analysis in PLAXIS LE. According to the expected levels of performance in terms of probability of failure by U.S. Army Corps of Engineers as seen in [9], the computed p_f at initial stage

is *unsatisfactory*. The unsatisfactory performance of the slope is not surprising at all, numerous slope failure incidents have been reported in the area [5], [12], [14]–[16]. There is a drastic rise in pf at the early stages which aligns with the drastic drop in FOS due to the high extreme rainfall intensity at that time. Increased rainfall intensity elevates the likelihood of failure as it swiftly generates positive porewater pressure, thereby diminishing shear strength parameters [1]. Conversely, lower rainfall intensity decreases the probability of failure due to the absence of these effects. It should be noted that the standards by U.S. Army Corps of Engineers considers that a slope with pf of 0.16 and above as *hazardous*. The slope of this case study reached the hazardous stage at day 16 of continuous rainfall and reaches a final pf of 0.355 after 30 days. Thus, the expected level of performance of the slope after 30 days extreme rainfall at 10 year-ARI is *hazardous*. It should be noted that the hazardous performance is in good agreement with numerous documented studies found in [5], [12], [14]–[16]. Furthermore, in real life scenario, fatal landslide has occurred in this slope before that result in deaths due to prolonged antecedent rainfall [5], [17]–[19]. The findings derived from PLAXIS LE models indicate the potential criticality of the slope in the event of a 30-day rainfall of a 10-year return period. Previous studies have demonstrated that landslides triggered by rainfall occurred in slopes within Hulu Kelang, particularly in areas with soils of moderate permeability, primarily due to extended antecedent rainfall [5], [12], [14]–[16]. Hence, the outcomes of this investigation align with documented studies, further supporting their validity.

4. Risk estimation and quantification results

From Figure 7, the retrogression distance, rL was calculated to be 150m. Sim et al. [20] formulated a relationship between retrogression distance, rL of a landslide and its subsequent runout, Lu which is, $Lu = 3.6322rL^{0.8475}$. Using the established empirical model, the runout is subsequently calculated at 254m which is a little higher than the actual runout that occurred (210m). The total travel distance from the crest to the toe of the slide will thus be approximately 404m. These estimates are a little more on the conservative side (real life total travel distance 330m). The model was made to give runout parameters on the conservative side and to provide a safety margin for emergency situations, avoiding underestimation of risk and hazard. As stated by [21], a conservative prediction could be highly suitable for initial evaluations of landslide susceptibility and hazard. In addition, although the prediction was conservative, it is not unrealistic as the model was developed on the basis of real life landslide cases [21]. With a ten year return period rainfall, (probability of occurrence of 0.1 (1 in 10)) and a resulting probability of slope failure of 35.5% or 0.355, the probability where a landslide would occur that would result in a total runout distance of 404m is thus computed to be at 0.0355. The estimated landslide affected zone is plotted in Figure 10 taking into account the total travel distance of 404m. The residential area comprises mainly of houses and its occupants were treated as elements of risk. The loss of human lives is the main focus for risk estimation. There are around 21 houses located in the affected area as seen in Figure 10.

The risk analysis approach was primarily built upon the framework outlined by Lee and Jones [22] and was adjusted and broadened according to the specific scenarios being examined. Consequently, a definition for risk analysis was formulated as follows:

$$\text{Risk} = P(\text{Event}) \times P(\text{Hit} | \text{Event}) \times P(\text{Damage} | \text{Hit}) \times C$$

The equation Risk equals the product of $P(\text{Event})$ multiplied by the conditional probabilities of $P(\text{Hit} | \text{Event})$ and $P(\text{Damage} | \text{Hit})$, all multiplied by the consequences (C) resulting from the landslide event. Here, $P(\text{Event})$ represents the anticipated likelihood of a landslide event occurring annually, $P(\text{Hit} | \text{Event})$ signifies the yearly probability of an element being impacted given a landslide event, considering both spatial and temporal probabilities of affecting elements at risk, $P(\text{Damage} | \text{Hit})$ denotes the yearly probability of damage occurring given that an element is impacted, measured on a scale between 0 and 1, and C signifies the consequences stemming from the landslide event.

In the context of this study, 'Damage' was interpreted to denote the occurrence of one or more deaths among the residents, effectively encapsulating the combined notions of 'Damage' and 'Consequences.' As a result, the equation is transformed into:

$$\text{Risk} = P(\text{Event}) \times P(\text{Hit} | \text{Event}) \times P(\text{Death} | \text{Hit}) \times C$$

Risk equals the product of $P(\text{Event})$ multiplied by the conditional probabilities of $P(\text{Hit} | \text{Event})$ and $P(\text{Death} | \text{Hit})$.

Figure 5 changes in FOS with time

Figure 6 Changes in probability of failure with time

Figure 7 Critical slip surface with lowest factor of safety after 30 days of extreme rainfall at 10-year ARI with GLE method

Figure 8 Relative influence of material parameters to FOS

Figure 9 Aerial views of the case study slope. Source: [12]

Figure 10 predicted runout of the potential landslide

4.1 P(Event)

According to Winter [23], landslide hazard, referred to as P(Event), is defined as the yearly probability of occurrence derived from historical data. This explicitly adopts a uniformitarian perspective, assuming that the past serves as a reference for future events. There remains a debate on the suitability of relying solely on historical natural process patterns as a predictor of future occurrences. For example, uncertainties arise regarding the projected qualitative rise in landslide frequency due to climate change [10], [24]. Furthermore, this method requires a complete landslide inventory which unfortunately is not ideal hence it will lead to complications in directly evaluating landslide hazard [25]–[27]. On the other hand, P(Event) can also be determined through the computation of the probability of failure of a slope [26], [28]. Hence, after conducting comprehensive probabilistic slope stability analyses, the likelihood of an annual occurrence (or frequency) of a landslide covering a total travel distance of 404 meters, capable of potentially damaging 21 houses situated on the slope in the case study, has been calculated to be P(Event) = 0.035.

4.2 P(Hit | Event)

When a landslide occurs on the slopes adjacent to the residential area within the study zone, the individuals residing in the houses are considered the potential vulnerable elements. This risk factor comprises two contributing aspects, specifically denoted as P(Wrong Place) and P(Wrong Time) [22]. The duration for which an asset or an individual remains susceptible to the hazard—being in the 'wrong place' at the 'wrong time'—can vary significantly. For instance, there exists a disparity in exposure between a person walking underneath an overhanging rock and someone occupying a stationary beach hut. [22]. The probability of being in the wrong place at the wrong time contributes to P(Hit | Event), which quantifies the probability of an occurrence described as a 'hit' connected with a landslide event.

In the context of individuals residing in the buildings, the determination of 'wrong place, wrong time' relied on the assessment of the amount of time these individuals spend inside the building throughout a year [26]. The frequency of occupancy by individuals is contingent upon the building's purpose. For individuals who occupy a residence almost constantly (such as elderly individuals or homemakers), probability for 'wrong place, wrong time' was considered as 1. However, for individuals in workplaces like offices, and students in schools, it was computed based on an average of 8 hours per day and 5 days per week, resulting in a value of 0.23. Regarding individuals present in the building during the night for 12 hours, the value will be taken as 0.5.

For the present study, the wrong place, wrong time will be taken as the probability where the residents are in the house when the landslide occurs. For simplification purposes, residents within this study are assumed to be at their residences from 7 pm to 7 am on Mondays to Fridays, totalling 12 hours. On weekends, it is presumed that they are absent from home for 8 hours, considering weekend activities like shopping, recreation, dining out, etc. Consequently, this assumption leads to a P(Hit | Event) of around 0.55. Accordingly, the probability where the house will be hit by the landslide when the resident is residing in the house will be computed as follows referencing documented workflows [22], [23]:

$$P(\text{Individual House Hit}) = P(\text{Event}) \times P(\text{Hit} | \text{Event}) = 0.035 \times 0.55 = 1.9\text{E-}2$$

4.3 P(Death | Hit)

P(Death | Hit), denoting human vulnerability (i.e., the likelihood of death upon the convergence of a house and landslide), was established as a quantitative representation of the probability of death resulting from an encounter with a landslide event affecting the house. It signifies the probability of fatality within the hazardous zones of the landslide (i.e., the 'Wrong Place' in either scenario).

Several determining factors influencing human vulnerability in the context of landslides are as follows [29], [30]:

- Whether the landslide covers the individual(s).
- Whether the individual(s) are outdoors or sheltered inside a vehicle or building.
- Whether the building collapses upon impact by debris.
- The nature of collapse in case of building collapse

A vulnerability rating of 1 signifies certain death, while a rating below 0.5 suggests a significantly higher chance of survival. Jaiswal et al. [26] recommends a value of 0.2 to 1.0 for people in reinforced concrete buildings where as the value of 1 (certain death) is recommended for residents residing in tin-shed buildings and 0.6 to 1.0 for residents of houses made of brick in mud without column structures. The likelihood of survival increases comparatively when an individual is inside a reinforced concrete building due to its greater structural strength. Several other documented studies also recommend the value of 0.2 for people inside a building inundated by landslides [31], [32]. According to previous reports, there was a landslide event that struck the same area in 1999 that results in 0 death [33]. In addition, there have been several other landslide that results in the destruction of bungalows with zero fatalities i.e. 2014 and 2022 Ampang landslide which is not far from the site of case study; 2016 Cameron Highlands landslide [34]–[36]. Harahap & Hazirah [37] proposes a vulnerability rate of 0.48 for the residents affected by landslides in the studied area; however, considering the preceding information, this latter figure appears notably high and somewhat conservative. The evidence provided above strongly indicates a notably reduced figure, and a value of 0.2 for P(Fatality | Hit) appears fitting within the context of the case study.

4.4 Societal Risk

The societal risk posed by landslide along the case study area is addressed using the F-N diagram, focusing on societal risk. The calculation for the societal risk associated with fatalities of inhabitants of the case study area was derived using the following equation [22]:

$$\text{Societal Risk} = \text{Individual Risk} \times \text{Exposed Population}$$

The specific group exposed to the landslide hazards are all the inhabitants of the houses in the study area, and their population size was determined based on reasonable assumption in accordance to the past reports [5], [38], [39]. In this study, house occupancies ranging from 1 to 8 per home has been taken as an estimate of for the at the site. Assuming equal exposure to landslide risks within the study area, the research categorized eight consequence classes based on house occupancy. This classification involved grouping houses into these classes, and subsequently, determining the quantity of houses within each class. The calculation of the probable fatalities (N) for each consequence class involved multiplying the house occupancy by the probability of fatality given a hit (P(Death | Hit)). The calculation for the F-N curve is tabulated in Table 2.

Various methods exist for generating data for the F-N diagram, outlined by Wong et al. [40], and Lee and Jones [22], none holding a superior claim to the other. In this study, Wong et al.'s [40] approach will be used as it has been proven to yield data better suited for plotting on the F-N diagram, resulting in a clearer representation [23], [41]. In comparison to the F-N curve of the case study site to other regions as shown in Sim et al. [19], [42], the F-N curve sits in between that of Nepal and Italy. The landslide risk of the site is also seen to be lower than that of Nilgiri Hills, India which is not surprising as the houses over there comprise various types including those made of tin-shed buildings, brick and mud without columns, as well as non-reinforced concrete houses [26]

From the F-N curve in Figure 11, it's evident that the value of F for N of 4 to 5 deaths falls between 10 years to 100 years. In reality, it didn't take more than 100 years after the construction of Bukit Antarabangsa for landslides to cause fatalities. The 4-5 deaths occurred in 2008, which is over 10 years after the development of Bukit Antarabangsa began around the time of the Highland Tower incident in 1993 [5], [43]. This aligns well with actual

reports of the landslide tragedy at the site. Furthermore, the F-N curve falls in the Unacceptable region when benchmarked against the risk criterion of Malaysia [19]. This also means that falls into the unacceptable category of yearly fatalities established by Hong Kong [42], [44]. This precariousness explains the landslide tragedy that occurred in real life at the site and also is of the utmost priority concerning slope mitigation or countermeasure strategies.

Table 2 Calculation for plotting F-N curves for residents at the site using. The consequence class simply refers to the different levels of house occupancy.

House Occupancy {2}/ Consequence Class	P(Death Hit) {3}	Number of Houses {4}	Frequency of Occurrence of N Deaths {5} = {1} x {3} x {4}	Cumulative Frequency of occurrence of N or more Deaths (F) {6}
1	0.169642857	1	3.25E-03	6.83E-02
2	0.169642857	2	6.50E-03	6.50E-02
3	0.169642857	3	9.75E-03	5.85E-02
4	0.169642857	5	1.63E-02	4.88E-02
5	0.169642857	4	1.30E-02	3.25E-02
6	0.169642857	3	9.75E-03	1.95E-02
7	0.169642857	2	6.50E-03	9.75E-03
8	0.169642857	1	3.25E-03	3.25E-03
{1} P(Individual House Hit)		1.92E-02		

Figure 11 F-N curve of the site benchmarked against the interim Malaysian Risk [19]

5. Limitation and future works

Uncertainties arose during the computation of population risk, primarily stemming from the challenge of estimating the likelihood of being in the 'wrong place at the wrong time'; the probability of death when a building is impacted by a landslide. Approaches for evaluating landslide risk should consistently account for these uncertainties and be applicable for implementation across extensive areas without excessive data demands. It is crucial to integrate these uncertainties into the analysis, presenting results as a spectrum of risk values, as demonstrated in this study where we assessed the range of expected losses from the affected zone owing to the landslide runout from the crest to the toe. Given the uncertainties associated with diverse input data in the risk analysis, it is advisable to conduct a comprehensive risk assessment on a large scale to inform the planning of

risk reduction strategies. Furthermore, these uncertainties can be modelled through various scenarios based on value ranges, employing simulation methods such as Monte Carlo simulation—a potential avenue for exploration in subsequent studies. In other words, incorporating uncertainty quantification methodologies to assess the confidence intervals of estimations would greatly enhance the robustness and reliability of the results. This will also further improve the applicability of the novel Malaysian risk criterion.

6. Summary and Conclusion

This paper illustrates how one can apply the proposed F-N risk criterion through Quantitative Risk Assessment (QRA). QRA emerges as a proficient method for comprehending, forecasting, and expressing the levels of risk associated with landslides at a specific location. In this section, QRA for the impact of a landslide on residents (potential fatalities) was reported for a hazardous site in Malaysia through a selected case study. Subsequently, runout of the landslide of the case study was predicted using the developed empirical model. Risk levels were estimated for elements at risk located along the run-out paths of the landslide and the overall risk to society was expressed using an F-N diagram, showcasing the practical implementation of the proposed Malaysian risk criterion.

The methodology takes into account the probability of a slope experiencing a landslide event, predicting both the runout distance and the potentially affected zone. It also factors in the conditional probabilities associated with a house being affected, given an event, and the likelihood of damage or death occurring when a house is affected. The analysis encompasses scenario involving a house being struck by a landslide.

Probabilistic slope stability analysis has shown that the site considered in this study is already in the *unsatisfactory* level of performance at initial stage by the standards of U.S. Army Corps of Engineers as seen in [9]. After 30 days of extreme rainfall, the performance further plummeted to *hazardous* level. The overall travel distance from the crest to the toe of the landslide was predicted to be around 404 m. These estimates are a little more on the conservative side as the real-life total travel distance was 330 m. The model was made to give runout parameters on the high side and to provide a safety margin for emergency situations, avoiding underestimation of risk and hazard. A conservative approach could be highly suitable for initial evaluations of landslide susceptibility and hazard [21]. The societal risk was conveyed through the F-N diagram, indicating that the annual risk falls within the unacceptable zone of the proposed Malaysian risk criterion [19].

Furthermore, the societal risk level well described the landslide disaster that occurred in real life at that site. This also shows that the vulnerability value of $P(\text{Death}/\text{Hit}) = 0.2$ used in this study seems fitting to context of the study. This is not surprising as previous reports regarding the landslide incident on the same slope brought about the destruction of 14 bungalows resulting in 4 to 5 deaths with 14 individuals sustained injuries and 93 people escaped unharmed [5], [38], [39]. The analyses function as an initial warning system for areas prone to significant landslides, capable of causing extensive damage. Conducting a thorough stability analysis of the slopes in specific regions is crucial to determine the risks and vulnerability of the population and to implement mitigation measures to minimize the potential risks to both lives and property. The assessment approach demonstrated in this paper can be applied to future hillside developments in Malaysia, especially when human lives are concerned.

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